

Reaction of rice varieties to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* in the greenhouse

Truong Thi Ngoc Chi and Luong Thi Phuong, Entomology Department, Cuulong Delta Rice Research Institute, Omon, Haugiang, Vietnam

We screened 181 rice varieties and lines against WBPH, using the seedling bulk test. Test lines were sown in 10-cm-long rows at 20 seeds/row in iron seedboxes 40 × 30 × 5 cm, filled 3 cm deep with fine soil.

Seedlings were infested 7 d after sowing with second- to third-instar

Resistance of rice varieties to WBPH in the greenhouse in Vietnam, 1990 wet season.

Variety	Damage score ^a	Variety	Damage score ^a
OM732-5-2-1-1-2-1-2-1	1	OM725-12-5-3-1-1-2	3
OM734-10-12-4-3-1	1	OM850-8-7-1	3
OM739-18-1-1-1-1	1	IR64	3
IR19661-10-1-2-3-2	1	IR68	3
OM35-1	3	IR49500	3
OM86-9	3	S.499B	3
OM554	3	NC492	3
OM723-3	3	DD1397	3
OM723-11	3	0005 Ba tuc ran	3
OM576	3	0581 C ₂	3
OM732-25-1-5-3-2-1	3	0855 Ca dung	3
OM732-29-9-3-5-7-9	3	TN1	9
OM732-41-2-5-3-2	3	Ptb 33	1

^aStandard evaluation system for rice.

WBPH nymphs at 5 nymphs/seedling. Plant damage was assessed when all plants of susceptible check TN1 had died.

Twenty-four lines showed resistance to WBPH (see table). ■

Stress tolerance — excess water

Tolerance of rice varieties for submergence

M. A. Hassan, A. K. Roy, N. C. Ghosh, and R. Thakur, Plant Breeding Department, Bihar Agricultural College, Rajendra Agricultural University, Sabour (Bhagalpur), India

Rice varieties cultivated in deepwater and lowland situations are prone to submergence by floods or heavy rains. In Bhagalpur region of Bihar, 1987 had abnormal rainfall: the average is 1.125 mm; in 1987, precipitation reached 1.990 mm. Lowland and deepwater

areas were inundated three to four times during Jun-Oct.

Altogether, 225 rices were under observation in replicated trials in the Rice Breeding Section of Agricultural College, Sabour, in various testing programs. The varieties or strains that survived submergence for 4-7 d 3-4 times are listed in the table.

These lines should perform well in areas prone to submergence and may also be useful as donor parents in crossing programs. Most of the tolerant lines are derived from crosses with 64-117 (28%), FR13A (22%), and FR43B (11%) as one parent. Lines involving these parents but did not survive formed only 2.6% of the 225 lines.

Many of the submergence-tolerant lines have good grain quality and improved plant type. Small quantities of seed can be made available on request. ■

Stress tolerance — adverse temperature

Phytohormone analog for protection of photosynthetic capacity and water use efficiency in rice during chilling

A. A. Flores-Nimedez and B. S. Vergara, Agronomy, Plant Physiology, and Agroecology Division, IRRI; and K. Doerffling, Institut fuer Allgemeine Botanik, Universitaet Hamburg, FRG

We investigated the effects of a new synthetic analog of the phytohormone abscisic acid (ABA) (provided by BASF, Ludwigshafen, FRG, coded LAB173711) alone and in combination with tetcyclacis (BASF), a growth retardant, on leaf photosynthetic rate and water use efficiency by rice plants during chilling.

Pregerminated seeds of IR36 were sown in trays. Two-week-old seedlings were sprayed with 10⁻⁴ mol LAB 173711/liter and with LAB173711 + tetcyclacis. After 24 h, the trays were transferred to a

Survival percentage of tolerant lines that survived 4-7 d submergence each time, along with other details.

Variety or culture	Parentage	Submergence score	Times (no.) of submergence
SBR3012-120-2-1	IR20/Pankaj	2	3
SBR3013-11-11-1-2	Pankaj/64-117	2	3
SBR3013-493-66-1-1	Pankaj/64-117	2	3
SBR3014-6-1	64-117/CN540	2	4
SBR3015-35-35-2-1-1	64-117/IR36	2	4
SBR3015-604-74-4-3-1	64-117/IR36	2	4
PTIR18-218-20-58-1-68	BS41/BKN19-3-4//IR4219-35-3-2	3	3
IR33383-9-1-1-3	IR52/IR13426-19-2//IR50	2	3
IET10164	FR13A/CN540	3	3
IET10168	FR13A/CN540	3	3
IET10172	FR13A/CNM539	2	3
IET10177	FR13A/CNM539	2	3
IET10180	FR43B/CNM539	2	3
IET10181	NC496/CNM539	2	3
IET10547	FR43B/CNM539	2	3
IET10567	CR94/Mahsuri	3	3
IET10596	CR94/Mahsuri	3	3
64-117 (Janki)	Pureline selection	2	3

water tank at 8 °C root temperature and 25 °C air temperature, 12 h photoperiod and kept there for 3 and 4 d, respectively. Net leaf photosynthetic rate and water use efficiency were measured using a steady state CO₂/H₂O porometer (Walz, Effeltrich, FRG) and a BINOS infrared gas analyzer (Heraeus, Hanau, FRG: provided by M. Dingkhun, IRRRI).

Chilling caused leaf yellowing, leaf wilting, and finally death of the seedlings. Net photosynthetic rate was 2.58 μmol/m² per s in the chilled but not chemically treated control and to 4.05 μmol/m² per s in plants sprayed with LAB173711 + tetcyclacis and kept at 8 °C for 3 d (see figure).

As chilling was prolonged, photosynthetic rate continued to decline to 2.86 μmol/m² per s in plants treated with

Water use efficiency (mmol CO₂/mol H₂O)

Changes in photosynthesis and water use efficiency of IR36 plants treated with LAB 17311 and LAB 17311 + tetcyclacis and kept at 8 °C for 3 and 4 d. Data are means ± S.E. of 5 measurements. IRRRI, 1990

LAB173711 + tetcyclacis and to 1.45 μmol/m² per s in the chilled but not chemically treated control. The water use efficiency was higher (10.7) in plants treated with LAB173711 + tetcyclacis than in control plants (5.5).

Use of abscisic acid analog LAB173711 alone was less efficient than combining it with tetcyclacis; that resulted in higher photosynthetic rate and water use efficiency. ■

Stress tolerance — adverse soils

Iron toxicity tolerance of rice cultivars in acid sulfate soils of Indonesia

H. Rosmini and Mukhlis, Banjarharu
Research Institute for Food Crops, P.O. Box 31, Banjarbaru, South Kalimantan, Indonesia

We screened 73 rice varieties and breeding lines for Fe toxicity tolerance in acid sulfate soils (Table 1) at Unit Tatas substation, Central Kalimantan, during 1987 wet season.

Seedlings were transplanted 21 d after seeding at 20- × 20-cm spacing in 1- × 3-m plots/variety. Fertilizer was urea at 90 kg N/ha and TSP at 60 and 0 kg P/ha. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with two replications. Fe toxicity was scored 8 wk after transplanting.

Of the 73 entries, 18 were found tolerant of Fe toxicity (Table 2).

IR18349-53-1-3-1-3, IR19661-13-3-2, IR31917-31-3-2, IR9217-6-2-2-2-3, ITA212, and Pankaj did not respond to P fertilization. ■

Table 1. Some chemical characteristics of the acid sulfate soil at Unit Tatas substation, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia.

Characteristic	0-20 cm deep	20-40 cm deep
pH (H ₂ O)	3.95	3.90
Total N (%)	0.41	0.19
Organic C (%)	2.78	1.70
Available P (ppm)	17.63	32.96
Exchangeable K (meq/100g)	0.19	0.13
SO ₄ ⁺ (%)	0.12	0.05
Al ₃ ⁺ (meq/100g)	14.19	15.70
Fe (meq/100g)	6.16	5.59
Na (meq/100g)	0.21	0.26
Particle size (%)		
Sand	0.22	0.21
Silt	33.41	31.14
Clay	66.37	68.65

Table 2. Fe toxicity tolerance and yield of rice on acid sulfate soils. Tatas, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia.

Variety or line	Fe toxicity score ^a		Grain yield ^b (g/plot)	
	With P	Without P	With P	Without P
BR51-120-2	4	5	609 f	357 h
BW267-3	3	4	2166 a	1887 a
CR261-7039-236	4	5	1932 b	1653 bc
IR13146-45-2	4	5	1167 de	1068 e
IR18349-53-1-3-1-3	4	4	1143 de	1512 c
IR19657-87-3-3	4	6	1833 b	1275 d
IR19661-13-3-2	3	5	1311 cd	1764 ab
IR21836-90-3	3	5	1179 de	1047 ef
IR31917-31-3-2	3	5	729 f	858 fg
IR6023-10-1-1	3	5	1878 b	1578 bc
IR9217-58-2-2	4	5	1104 e	804 g
IR9217-6-2-2-2-3	4	5	1110 e	1479 c
ITA212	4	5	1443 c	1608 bc
ITA230	4	5	1317 cd	1194 de
Pankaj	4	5	1317 cd	1605 bc
Rohy15-WAR-3-3	4	5	1335 cd	1179 de
WAR52-384-3-2-2	4	4	1392 c	1107 de
Kapuas	3	4	2184 a	1650 bc

^a By the Standard evaluation System for rice. ^b In a column, values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.